

ABOUT THE METHOD OF MATHEMATICAL INDUCTION

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Abstract. In this article, the history of the creation of the mathematics induction method, its application in different disciplines, different definitions and examples.

Keywords: mathematics, physics, induction, deduction, parallelogram, fact, event.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada matematika induksiya metodikasi yaratilish tarixi, turli fanlarda qo'llanilishi, turli ta'riflar va misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: matematika, fizika, induksiya, deduksiya, parallelogramm, fakt, hodisa.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена история создания метода математической индукции, его применение в разных дисциплинах, различные определения и примеры.

Ключевые слова: математика, физика, индукция, дедукция, параллелограмм, факт, событие.

Before talking about the method of mathematical induction, let's analyze the concept of analogy. In the ancient Greeks, the sign of simile was originally expressed as a proportion of numbers. For example, $25 : 5 = 35 : 7$. Later, the word simile began to be applied to shapes and other things. Let's look at examples. The following forms are given:

It is required to find a pair of similar shapes.

According to which property, the question of choosing these pairs is raised. Solving this problem has been left to the computer. The computer compared the shapes, plotted the results on a sheet of paper and wrote the equation $X:Y=x:y$.

At present, such analogies are used in all sciences. Analogy is widely used in chemistry, biology, physics and geology.

Physics. The law of propagation of sound in air was established based on the phenomenon of propagation of waves of this phenomenon on the surface of water.

There are such problems in mathematics that some assumptions turn out to be wrong according to the final results. One of such issues concerns P. Ferma, who was born in 1644:

P. Ferma assumed that all natural numbers in the form $f(n) = n^2 + n + 41$ were prime numbers and only checked numbers from 1 to 39. But if $n=40$ numbers are set, the result will be a complex number. His mistake was that by computing $f(n) = n^2 + n + 41$ for some eigenvalues (this is a particular assertion), the value of $f(n) = n^2 + n + 41$ is prime for any natural number n came to the general conclusion that no.

L. Euler said the truth about simple induction leading to error: "In mathematics, when a statement about an infinite set is made, examination of a finite set cannot replace proof."

The difference between mathematics and other sciences is that this science builds its theory on a deductive basis. Conclusions are divided into two types: general and specific. Let us give examples of general conclusions: The diagonals of any parallelogram are bisected at the point of intersection. All numbers ending in zero are divisible by five. Any equilateral triangle has an axis of symmetry.

Specific conclusions corresponding to these examples: The diagonals of the parallelogram ABCD are bisected at the point of intersection. 150 is divisible by 5. If a given triangle is equilateral, then such a triangle has an axis of symmetry.

The transition from a general statement to a specific statement is called a deduction.

The transition from a specific statement to a general statement is called induction. Induction can lead to both correct and incorrect results.

The induction method is widely used in mathematics, but it is more accurate should be used.

Confirmation: The following three-digit numbers: 140, 150, 250 are divisible by 5.

Conclusion: 1) All numbers ending in zero are divisible by 5 (true), 2) all three-digit numbers are divisible by 5 (false).

Such a question arises. In mathematics to draw the correct conclusion

How to use the induction method? What methods are used to check the phenomenon of infinite numbers?

This method was first used in 1321. The mathematical induction method used by Gersonides, which we use today, was developed by B. Pascal and Ya. Bernoulli suggested. This method was also used by some ancient Greek scientists.

Until the second half of the 19th century, this method was considered the main method of proof. From this period, after the scientific works of O. Boltsano, O. L. Cauchy, K. F. Gauss, N. H. Abel, inductive proofs partially lost their importance in mathematics.

Deduction is the application of a pre-existing general truth, a general principle, to smaller, isolated cases, based on the rules of logical reasoning and logic. In deduction, a general hypothesis is tested through existing individual cases in life. This general principle already exists, and cases are studied only to verify and apply this principle. Logic is the primary factor here; and experience is secondary.

Induction is a general conclusion made by observing a certain number of isolated facts, events and processes, based on these observations. According to this method, a large number of

objects or processes are carefully observed and studied, and then a single, general conclusion is drawn from these observations. In induction, logic does not have a primary role, experience has a primary role. From the facts to the rule, from many isolated examples to a single general conclusion. A general conclusion is developed from specific circumstances and opinions.

Mathematical induction is a method of proving a mathematical statement based on the principle of mathematical induction:

If $A(1)$ is proved, then $A(x)$ is proved depending on the natural parameter x is considered to be proved and it is assumed that $A(n)$ is true for an arbitrary natural number n if done, $A(n+1)$ is correct for $n+1$.

The proof of statement $A(1)$ is the first step of induction,

The proof of $A(n+1)$ from the hypothesis for $A(n)$ is called an induction transition. In this called the induction parameter, it is inductive to assume $A(n)$ in proving $A(n+1)$ is called a hypothesis.

Theorem 1. The statement is true for $n = 1$.

Theorem 2. Assuming that the assertion is true for arbitrary $n=k$, then the confirmation is considered true for the next $n=k+1$ natural number.

If both these theorems are proved, it is mathematical induction based on the principle, the assertion is true for any natural number n is concluded.

Reminder. Not for all natural numbers, but m greater than or equal to n for natural numbers, it is necessary to prove the assertion by induction. Such the proof is done as follows.

Theorem 1. In $n = m$, the statement is true.

Theorem 2. In $n=k$, the assertion is correct, $k \geq m$. In $n = k + 1$, the confirmation is appropriate it is necessary to prove that

1. Example. Any natural number is equal to the next natural number.

Proof.

$$k=k+1 \quad (1)$$

let's assume that it is. In that case

$$k+1=k+2 \quad (2)$$

is formed. In fact, if we add 1 to both sides of (1), we get (2). From this, it follows that if the statement is true for $n=k$, then it is also true for $n=k+1$.

Result. All natural numbers are equal. The error of the result is self-evident. Where does this error come from?

The mistake is that the 1 point necessary for the application of the principle of mathematical induction was not proved, only 2 points were proved.

1 point is called the basis of induction. In point 2, the basis of induction is expanded for any natural number n .

If point 1 is not verified and only point 2 is proved, then there is no basis for induction, so what is proved is meaningless because there is no basis to extend.

If only 1 point is proved without 2 points being proved, then a basis for performing induction is created, but there is no rule for expanding this basis for any number n . In the process of proving by the method of mathematical induction, the following cases may occur.

If the statement $A(n)$ is true based on inductive reasoning, it can be proved using the method of mathematical induction. If the statement $A(n)$ expressed by induction is correct, its error can be easily determined in the process of proving 2 points.

We explain the method of mathematical induction in examples.

Example 2. Prove that the value of the expression $n^3 + 11n$ is divisible by 6 for all natural values of N .

Proof. We use the method of mathematical induction.

let $n=1$. In that case

$$n^3 + 11n = 1^3 + 11 \cdot 1 = 1 + 11 = 12$$

we will have 12 is divisible by 6.

If $n=k$, the value of the expression $n^3 + 11n$ is equal to the number $k^3 + 11k$. We assume that this number is divisible by 6.

In $N=k+1$. This $n^3 + 11n = (k+1)^3 + 11(k+1)$

we prove that the expression is divisible by 6. For this, we open the parentheses in the above expression and it will look like this.

$$n^3 + 11n = (k+1)^3 + 11(k+1) = (k^3 + 11k) + 3k(k+1) + 12$$

According to our hypothesis, the number $n^3 + 11n$ is divisible by 6. Since $k(k+1)$, which is the product of two consecutive natural numbers, is divisible by 2, $3k(k+1)$

number is divisible by 6. that is why

$$(k^3 + 11k) + 3k(k+1) + 12$$

number is divisible by 6. So, in all natural values of n , the expression is divisible by 6.

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